

Examining Pre-Service Teachers' Beliefs about the Nature of Science in the Context of Botswana

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Abstract

There is a general concern that being unaware of pre-service teachers' beliefs about NOS can be futile to teacher education and development in science education. Thus a quantitative case study approach was employed in the investigation of pre-service science teachers' beliefs about the nature of science. 78 pre-service teachers of science were randomly selected from a local university in Botswana. Participants responded to a questionnaire using a 4 point Likert scale (Cronbach's alpha coefficient of .743). Data analysis revealed that pre-service teachers' beliefs about NOS aspects were inconsistent. However, participants' overall beliefs about the NOS were progressive. These findings have implications on training of science education teachers and development of scientific literacy in Botswana.

Keywords: *beliefs, Botswana, nature of science, pre-service teacher, science education*

1.0 Introduction

The article departs from a broader study which explored student-teachers' beliefs about teaching and learning of science as well as beliefs about the nature of science (NOS) (Patrick, 2019). Although Patrick's (2019) generated both quantitative and qualitative data, his report was based on qualitative data. Therefore, the purpose of this article is to report on quantitative procedures used to derive data and the inferred findings on pre-service teachers' beliefs about the nature of science.

1.1 What is NOS?

Attempts to define the nature of science have not yet yielded an absolute definition. Definitions derived from philosophical elements alone are highly contested. There are suggestions that to understand 'nature' of science goes beyond epistemology to the inclusion of history, sociology and psychology (Lederman, 2004). Approaching NOS in this light broadens the NOS net and further complicates the issue of defining NOS. For the time being, educators and researchers in science education have typically embraced Lederman, Abd-El-Khalick, Bell & Schwartz's (2002) claim that although NOS is challenging to define, there are some aspects of NOS which are common in various fields. Most literature has adopted seven aspects of NOS suggested by Lederman et al., (2002). These include; (a) Tentative, (b) Empirical, (c) Observation & inferential, (d) Creative & imaginative, (e) Social & cultural, (f) Scientific theory & law, and (g) Theory laden.

These seven aspects of NOS have been instrumental in NOS research and instruction. Researchers, scientists and science educators are currently using NOS aspects whenever they are dealing with "issues such as what science is, how it works, the epistemological and ontological foundations of science, how scientists function as a social group and how society influences and reacts to scientific endeavors" (Clough & Olson, 2008, p. 143). The wide use of these seven aspects in measuring NOS makes them theoretical foundations for empirical studies on NOS. Therefore, this study uses aspects of NOS as a criterion for evaluating Nature of Science beliefs of pre-service teachers.

1.2 NOS in science education

Debates about the place and function of Nature of Science in science education are inconsistent. However, there is a consensus that NOS is likely to provide teachers with an epistemological foundation of scientific knowledge construction, principles guiding scientific practices and the value of scientific knowledge (Hodson, 2014; Tsai, 2002). Understanding NOS is fundamental to teachers' conception of the knowledge of

science content, which plays a critical role in their pedagogical thoughts of how to link science content to teaching, learning, assessment and feedback (Hassan, 2011; Lederman, Lederman & Antink, 2013; McComas, 2017).

1.3 Science teachers' NOS perspectives

There is a wide range of literature exploring the views of teachers with regard to the nature of science. In a previous study by Akerson and Donnelly (2008), science pre-service teachers (N=21) enrolled for master's degree program were investigated for their views of NOS. Interviews helped to discern that 17 pre-service teachers held adequate views about NOS while 4 pre-service teachers held inadequate views of NOS. Akerson and Donnelly (2008) categorized pre-service teachers' views into three NOS categories; fully informed, adequate and inadequate views. These categories corresponded to a developed understanding of NOS, a challenging view of NOS and misconceptions about NOS respectively.

Koksall and Cakiroglu (2010) used open-ended questionnaires and knowledge interviews to assess teachers' NOS conceptions. Their findings point to the existence of some misunderstandings on dimensions of the Nature of Science. These findings are consistent with other studies. For example, NOS views of science teachers in Turkey were examined through questionnaire items and found to hold naïve views on many dimensions of NOS (Aslan & Tasar, 2013). A similar study conducted by Mihaladiz and Dogan (2014) in Turkey also reported that a majority of participants held naïve views about NOS.

Sangsa-ard and Thathong (2013) examined 116 Junior High school science teachers' understanding of NOS in Thailand. All participants responded to an open-ended questionnaire of NOS while 10% were also interviewed in order to validate findings. Results indicated that 63.3% of teachers held intermediate views of NOS while 32.7% held naïve views. According to Sangsa-ard and Thathong (2013), intermediate views corresponded to holding contradictory views (both informed and naïve) on aspects of NOS.

Sumranwanich and Yuenyong (2014) studied NOS views of first year master degree in-service science teachers enrolled in a course named History and Philosophy in Science. Sumranwanich and Yuenyong administered a View on Science Education (VOSE) after participants had explicit NOS teaching. Findings revealed that science in-service teachers held differing views on different aspects of NOS. For instance, most participants were of views that supported tentative science knowledge while a lesser number of "graduate students seemed to hold the position of the universal scientific method questionnaire" (Sumranwanich & Yuenyong, 2014, p. 2448).

In essence, literature shows that teachers of science, whether in-service or pre-service, hold certain views about aspects of the nature of science (Tsai, 2002). These views are liable to change when interventions like explicit NOS instruction are involved in promoting NOS conception (Abd-El-Khalick, 2012; Cakmakci, 2012; Halloun, 2001; Sumranwanich & Yuenyong, 2014).

1.4 Rationale for the study

This study was inspired by the idea that science teachers or student-teachers actually have both espoused and tacit beliefs about the nature of science regardless of their contextual and demographic features. By implication, Botswana science in-service and pre-service teachers supposedly shelter beliefs about NOS. Therefore, unearthing these beliefs might prove valuable in the development of innovative in-service interventions or in the development of pre-service teachers.

We are concerned that being unaware of status quo of science teachers' beliefs about NOS can be futile to the teachers' pedagogical thoughts and practices in science. NOS views are prone to remain unchallenged and unchanged more especially when they are unknown. Therefore, this study purposed to provide a general overview of science pre-service teachers' conceptions about the nature of science in Botswana. The following questions were answered;

- 1) What are science pre-service conceptions about the nature of science?
- 2) What is the significant difference in science pre-service teachers' conceptions of NOS based on demographic characteristics?

2.0 Methodology

Quantitative methods were employed to gain an overview sense of student-teachers' perspectives about the Nature of Science in Botswana. This research approach was underpinned by positivist paradigm which is characterized by its objectivity and robustness in providing statistical analysis of data (Cohen, Manion & Morrison, 2007). Under this methodological approach, we chose to use a case study design to guide the research decisions and practices (Wiersma & Jurs, 2009; Creswell, 2003). Participants in this study were bound by common features; being in the same university and they were all teacher trainees for science subjects (Biology, Chemistry and Physics) under the same Faculty of Education in the department of Mathematics and Science Education (DMSE).

2.1 Sample

Random sampling was used to select participants (n=78) based on their consent. Majority of participants were females (66.7%). The sample comprised of 25.6% student-teachers in Year 2, 26.9% in Year 3, 33.3% in Year 4 and 14.1% in Postgraduate Diploma in Education (PGDE). The composition of pre-service teachers by subject specialization was predominated by Biology Education at 52.6%, followed by Chemistry Education at 28.2% and Physics Education at 19.2%. The majority of the sampled pre-service teachers (65.4%) had no prior teaching experience.

2.2 Data collection

Data was collected from participants through the use a questionnaire with 13 items. Three items sought out demographic information of participants while ten items were concerned with their NOS beliefs. A Likert scale of 1 up to 4 was used. 1 represented Strongly Disagree, 2-Disagree, 3-Agree and 4-Strongly Agree. Items 1, 2, 5, 7 & 9 were negative statements. The reliability of the questionnaire was reported at .743 Cronbach alpha, indicating a good internal consistency of items in measuring the construct of NOS (Bless & Kathurima, 2001).

Ethical concerns were addressed before data collection. For instance, we obtained consent after making certain that participants understood issues of voluntary participation, privacy and confidentiality (Davison, 2002; Stake, 1998). Participants obtained, completed and returned questionnaires with a 100% return rate.

2.3 Data analysis

Perspectives towards aspects of NOS were analysed using a traditional/modern dichotomy. Student-teachers were either traditionally oriented regarding an aspect of NOS or they held modern views. Analysis using descriptive statistics was used to provide a sense of student-teachers' perspectives towards questionnaire items.

To further analyse an individual student-teacher's general NOS perspective, we computed percentage frequency of Traditionally perceived items out of 10 items (T/10). Once individual's general NOS perspective were computed, we developed an analytic framework which classified NOS perspectives in a continuum of five categories. These categories were naïve, intermediate naïve, emergent, progressive and informed. Descriptions of these categories and cut-off points for each category are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Categories in the NOS perspective continuum

Category	Description	Data (T/10*100)
Naive	Proportion of Traditionally perceived NOS aspects are more, with less to none existent Modern ones. High dominance of Traditional NOS aspects. Fully developed misconception of NOS.	80 to 100%
Intermediate naive	Traditional NOS aspects are high with a considerable number of Modern ones. Moderate dominance of Traditional aspects of NOS. developing misconceptions of NOS.	51 to 69%
Emergent	Equal proportion of T vs. M perceptions on aspects of NOS. Contradictory understanding of NOS	50%
Progressive	The proportion of Traditionally perceived aspects of NOS is less than Modern ones. Moderate dominance of NOS aspects. Developing understanding of NOS.	21 to 49%
Informed	There very few to none Traditionally perceived aspects of NOS. High dominance of modern NOS aspects. Fully developed understanding of NOS.	0 to 20%

Individuals' holistic NOS perspectives were subjected to further analysis to determine whether differences existed in accordance to independent variables (gender, level of study, teaching experience and subject of specialization).

3.0 Results

The ultimate purpose of this study was to provide a general overview of university going science student-teachers' NOS perspectives.

3.1 Views on aspects of NOS

A summary of descriptive statistics of science student-teachers' perspectives regarding NOS items from the questionnaire is given in Table 2. Mean scores equal and/or above 3 were indicative of agreement with NOS item whereas mean scores less than 3 were indicative of disagreement. Results indicate that a majority of science student-teachers held modern views concerning items 3, 4, 5, 6 and 10 while items 1,2, 7, 8, and 9 were traditionally perceived. These views were significant at 5% level of significance with an exception of item 8.

Table 2. Items on elements of Nature of Science

Item no.	Items from questionnaire	M	SD
1	Science is a collection of rules and procedures that prescribe how to solve a problem.	3.62	.629
2	Science gives a true account of the natural world.	3.33	.715
3	Science involves creativity, luck and new ideas	3.60	.566
4	Scientific discoveries and new ideas are influenced by cultural and social attitudes as well as myths	3.38	.871
5	Fundamental to science is its logical, correct and preciseness	2.55	1.028
6	Science has practical relevance in solving everyday problems and tasks.	3.32	.655
7	A fact in science is a truth which can never be changed.	3.71	.512
8	The evaluation of scientific knowledge varies with changes in situations	2.88	1.128
9	Scientific knowledge can come from dreams, intuition and hunches.	2.67	1.113
10	Scientific knowledge is free of human perspectives	2.04	1.012

3.2 General perspective of NOS

Figure 1 below shows that pre-service teachers hold beliefs which range from Intermediate naïve to Informed along the NOS perspective continuum. A higher proportion of science pre-service teachers *informed* views (56.4%), followed by 32.1% of those who held views which are *progressive*. The table also shows that amongst the sampled pre-service teachers, none of them exhibited perspectives which are completely *naïve*, while 5.1% held *intermediate naïve* perspectives compared to 6.4% who held *emergent* perspectives.

Figure 1. NOS perspectives of science pre-service teachers

Although it would seem that the highest number of science pre-service teachers held *informed* views about NOS, descriptive analysis shows that these pre-service teachers generally held *progressive* views ($M=24.10\%$, $SD=17.391$).

3.3 Differences in NOS beliefs

Question 2 evaluates whether science pre-service teachers' general NOS perspectives differed by gender, subject of specialization or their level of study as well as whether they had teaching experience or not.

Gender

According to Table 4, each category of the NOS perspective continuum is dominated by female science pre-service teachers. For instance, among 56.4% of respondents who held a generally informed perspective of NOS, the majority were female (68.2%) whereas there were 31.8% male pre-service teachers. In 32.1% of science pre-service teachers who held progressive beliefs about NOS, females were (64.0%) more than males (36.0%), while pre-service teachers holding emergent beliefs (6.4%) were composed of 60.0% females and 40.0% males, and lastly the 5.1% of respondents who held intermediate naïve beliefs about NOS were comprised of 75.0% females and 25.0% males.

Table 4. Science pre-service teachers' NOS perspectives by gender

NOS perspective of participants		% within NOS perspective of participants	Gender of Participants		Total
			Male	Female	
Intermediate naive			25.0%	75.0%	5.1%
Emergent			40.0%	60.0%	6.4%
Progressive			36.0%	64.0%	32.1%
Informed			31.8%	68.2%	56.4%
Total			33.3%	66.7%	100.0%

Mean scores shows that both female (24.42, $SD=17.536$) and male (23.46, $SD=17.422$) student-teachers held generally progressive NOS beliefs. To further compare means for statistical difference, an Independent t-test statistic was used at .05% level of significance. Using Levene's Test for Equality of Variances, the null

hypothesis for equal variances were assumed ($F=.051$, $p=.821 >.05\%$) and it was found that there was no significant difference between NOS beliefs of female and male student-teachers ($t=-.229$, $df=76$ & $p=.820 >.05\%$).

Teaching experience

With regard to teaching experience, pre-service teachers with and those without teaching experience both espoused progressive views of NOS. An independent t-test statistic was conducted to examine whether there was a relationship between teaching experience and NOS perspectives. Equal variance was assumed ($F=1.359$, $p=.551 >.05\%$). Table 5 depicts that there was no statistical significant difference between student-teachers with teaching experience ($M=25.19$, $SD=16.022$) and those without teaching experience ($M=23.53$, $SD=18.201$).

Table 5. Independent samples t-test comparing NOS views by teaching experience

	t-test for equality of Means				
	t	df	Sig.(2 tailed)	Mean diff	Std. error Diff
NOS perspectives of pre-service teachers	.398	76	.692	1.656	4.162

Subject specialization

On the question of whether pre-service teachers' subject specialization had a relationship with their espoused general NOS views, evidence showed that pre-service teachers training to teach Biology and Physics espoused progressive views about NOS while Chemistry teacher trainees seemed to espouse more informed views of NOS (Table 6). Pre-service teachers specializing in Chemistry Education seemed to hold views which were slightly different from pre-service teachers.

Table 6. Teachers' NOS perspectives by subject specialization

Pre-service teachers' specialization	N	M	SD	Std. Error
Biology Education	41	24.63	18.316	2.861
Chemistry Education	15	19.33	16.242	4.194
Physics Education	22	26.36	16.488	3.515
Total	78	24.10	17.391	1.969

To confirm whether there was a significant difference in pre-service teachers' espoused NOS beliefs in relation to their subject of specialization, Anova was computed and the outcome indicated that there were no significant differences in NOS views within and between subject of specializations ($F=.764$, $p=.469 >.05\%$).

Table 7. Anova output for comparison of NOS beliefs by subject of specialization

NOS perspective of pre-service teachers					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	465.243	2	232.622	.764	.469
Within Groups	22821.936	75	304.292		
Total	23287.179	77			

Level of study

Analysis of science pre-service teachers' perspectives of the nature of science according to their level of study revealed that Year 2 ($M=23.50$, $SD= 18.144$), Year 3 ($M=24.29$, $SD= 17.196$) and Year 4 ($M=26.54$, $SD= 14.681$) held NOS beliefs which were progressive compared to PDGE enrollees who held informed beliefs about NOS ($M=19.09$, $SD= 23.002$). However, Table 8 indicates that respondents from Year 2 to PGDE held NOS beliefs which were not significantly different from each other ($F=.473$, $p=.702 >.05\%$).

Table 8. Anova results comparing NOS perspectives by level of study

NOS perspective of pre-service teachers					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	438.523	3	146.174	.473	.702
Within Groups	22848.656	74	308.766		
Total	23287.179	77			

4.0 Discussion

The primary objective of this study was to assess and identify science pre-service teachers' beliefs about the nature of science. Two main questions were asked; 1) what are science pre-service conceptions about the nature of science, and 2) what is the significant difference in science pre-service teachers' conceptions of NOS based on demographic characteristics?

Findings revealed that science pre-service teachers held progressive beliefs about the nature of science. These findings are consistent with what Akerson and Donnelly (2008) and Cakmakci (2012) found in their investigations. Interestingly, pre-service science teachers' beliefs do not seem to align to whether a country is developed or developing. For instance, Sangsa-ard and Thathong (2014) found out that pre-service teachers in Thailand predominantly held naïve views about NOS which is comparably different from our current findings. This is however not conclusive, more especially since our study was not comparative.

Although beliefs about NOS are progressive, a quick glance at views concerning individual aspects reflect a complex composition of traditional and contemporary views on aspects of NOS, with more gravitation towards contemporary views (Aslan & Tasar, 2013; Akerson & Donnelly, 2008; Koksai & Cakirogiu, 2010; Mihadiz & Dogan, 2013; Mellado, 1997). It is apparent from the incoherent views on aspects of the nature of science that science pre-service teachers do not have a clear understanding of NOS. This outcome may be explained by previous science learning experiences which lacked explicit NOS learning. In particular, philosophy statements underpinning both the primary and secondary school science curricula in Botswana make references suggestive of the use of NOS in teaching and learning of science while there is no emphasis on NOS teaching (Mihadiz & Dogan, 2013; Sumranwanich & Yuenyong, 2014). On the other hand, Tafa (2012) evidenced that Botswana teachers favored authoritarian teaching methods which could also mean that teacher educators do not plan for and utilize participatory and interactive methodologies that would otherwise cultivate and foster NOS reflection. Or perhaps these findings are due to challenges that are entirely linked to personal knowledge and proficiencies of pre-service teachers. For instance, Koosimile and Suping (2011) contended that pre-service teachers lack the proficiency to critically debate issues during their learning. Is it possible that the inconsistencies in pre-service teachers' views on NOS aspects could be a result of their failure to engage with and reflect on NOS critically? Inconsistencies in perceptions of NOS aspects raise interesting questions highlighting the need for further exploration.

It was also found that pre-service science teachers' beliefs about NOS did not differ significantly by gender, previous teaching experiences, subject of specialization and level of study (Hassan, 2011; Mihadiz, 2012; Mihadiz & Dagon, 2013; Pelissier & Venturini, 2011). This shows that the time that pre-service teachers spent training to teach science-related subjects or having actually taught before, does not actually affect the way they view the nature of science. One would have expected that participants with prior teaching experiences will perceive NOS more differently because they had opportunities to reflect on NOS during their planning and instructional practices. Moreover, post graduate pre-service teachers holding general science first degrees would also have been expected to espouse beliefs about NOS which were different due to their learning experiences

which were a 'shadow' of the scientific enterprise and norms (Moeed, 2013). Our findings contradicted those of Pomeroy (1993), who found that scientists espoused more traditionalistic views of NOS compared to science teachers. We are likening PGDE pre-service teachers to scientists because PGDE pre-service teachers spent prolonged time in a more 'scientific world' where they might have been "initiated into the norms" of that world (Pomeroy, 1993, p. 269).

4.1 Conclusion

In general, university pre-service teachers in Botswana held progressive beliefs concerning the nature of science. However, we found out that there was no significant difference in espoused NOS beliefs due to gender, previous teaching experience, subject specialization as well as level of study. Conducting baseline investigations such as this one could prove helpful for teacher educators in data based decision-making for pedagogical reasons. Knowing pre-service teachers' views on NOS aspects can serve as reference point for explicit NOS instruction. Moreover, pre-service teachers show good understanding of nature of science which might be a good for fostering scientific literacy. We suggest that more robust qualitative research to provide insights into fully understanding issues around how science pre-service teachers' NOS beliefs manifest.

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